

ASSORTMENT ANALYSIS OF LOCAL SYSTEMIC ANTIVIRAL MEDICINES IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN BY PRESCRIPTION AND OVER-THE-COUNTRY STATUS

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Relevance: this study analyzed the market for systemic antiviral drugs and presented the results using the content analysis method. The data source was the "Drug Audit" program database of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which records the import and local production of drugs and medical devices into the country for 2017-2023. The formulation indicators of local systemic antiviral drugs in the Republic of Uzbekistan were analyzed. Analyzing the results recorded in 2023 based on the results of this study, it is revealed that 45% (3 million) of the studied market segment in the Republic of Uzbekistan are non-prescription drugs and 55% (3.6 million) are prescription drugs. The data presented is of great importance in providing the population and industry experts with an understanding of the formulation indicators of systemic antiviral drugs, as well as in conducting government procurement.

Purpose of the study: to conduct a content analysis of the packaging of systemic antiviral drugs imported into the pharmaceutical market of the Republic of Uzbekistan according to their formulation parameters and, based on this, to plan the next stage of marketing or pharmacoeconomic research.

Materials and methods: the research method was carried out using the previously widely used content analysis method.

Results: the indicators of prescription and non-prescription categories of systemic antiviral drugs imported into the Republic of Uzbekistan were studied. The results of the study can be seen in the diagram below.

This chart shows that in the first three years, the import of non-prescription drugs (2017 - 1.95 million; 2018 - 2.2 million; 2019 - 2.18 million) was higher than that of prescription drugs (2017 - 1.71 million; 2018 - 1.2 million; 2019 - 1.4 million). However, by 2020, the number of systemic antiviral drugs in the pharmaceutical market of our country has increased significantly, and non-prescription drugs (3.5 million) have significantly replaced prescription drugs (5.1 million). The study found that this unusual growth in 2020 was due to the unusually high share of over-the-counter

medicines in 2020, in addition to the "Acyclovir"-containing medicines, the "Inosine pranobex" and "Umifenovir"-containing medicines. In line with the similarly unusually sharp growth in prescription medicines, the "Acyclovir"-containing medicines and the Remdesivir-containing medicines had a significant impact. It should be noted that the "Remdesivir"-containing medicines began to be used in the local pharmaceutical market in 2020, and by 2023 they were not recorded in the market indicators at all. During the study period 2021-2023, the number of imported prescription drugs (2021 - 3.8 million; 2022 - 4.1 million; 2023 - 3.6 million) continued to exceed the number of imported non-prescription drugs (2021 - 2.7 million; 2022 - 2.7 million; 2023 - 3 million).

Conclusions: according to the results of the study, by 2020, the number of imported items of systemic antiviral drugs will increase sharply, and the import of prescription drugs will exceed the import of over-the-counter drugs by 2.4 million packages, which can be explained by the pandemic (Covid-19) that began in our country in 2020. Comparing the first year of our study, 2017, with 2023, it can be seen that over-the-counter drugs increased from 1.95 million to 3 million, and prescription drugs increased from 1.71 million to 3.6 million.